

Terracotta Figurines of Adults with Infants in Ancient Italy and Greece: Comparative Data, Contexts, and Research Framework

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This contribution presents a comparative analysis of terracotta figurines depicting adults with infants from ancient Italy and mainland Greece, including the Aegean islands, spanning from the Archaic period to the beginning of the Roman Imperial age (excluding material securely dated to the Common Era). The study synthesises nearly a decade of research and is developed within the framework of the ongoing project *M-othering in Ancient Greece through the Lens of Votive Religion*, hosted at **Comenius University in Bratislava** and funded by **NextGenerationEU through the Slovak Recovery and Resilience Plan** (project no. **09I01-03-V03-00008**).

Methodologically, the research combines typological analysis with close attention to depositional contexts in order to move beyond a purely iconographic approach. The theoretical framework draws on Lived (Ancient) Religion, understood as practice-based and situational rather than institutional or doctrinal, and integrates this perspective with an analytical focus on caregiving as a set of relational and socially embedded practices. Concepts such as *kourotrophia*—conceived as culturally embedded processes of “making a child grow”—and *othermothering* are employed as heuristic tools to decentre modern assumptions about family structure and to conceptualise “mothering” as a spectrum of shared, negotiated, and delegated forms of care rather than as a fixed biological role.

A central aim of the study is to compare patterns of production, circulation, and ritual use of figurines representing adults with infants across different cultural and regional contexts of the ancient Mediterranean. The Italian evidence discussed here is based on substantially stable and previously published corpora and provides a solid comparative baseline. In central Italy, figurines depicting adults with infants are exceptionally abundant and often characterised by serial and standardised production. They are predominantly associated with sanctuary contexts closely connected to civic space, suggesting that concerns related to fertility, childbirth, infant survival, and early childcare could be publicly ritualised and embedded within collective religious practices. The typological repertoire in these regions is comparatively wide and allows for multiple visual configurations of adult–infant relationships, including representations of shared caregiving and parental responsibility that extend beyond the isolated mother–child dyad.

In Hellenised areas of southern Italy and in Sicily, the phenomenon appears on a more limited scale and shows a stronger association with funerary contexts. Here, figurines seem to operate primarily within practices of commemoration, mourning, and family memory, rather than as public votive offerings. These established patterns from the Italian peninsula provide an essential framework for comparison with the Greek evidence.

The Greek corpus, which constitutes the core focus of the ongoing project, is still under systematic expansion and refinement. Preliminary analysis nevertheless reveals markedly different tendencies. Figurines depicting adults with infants are comparatively less numerous and display a highly fragmented regional distribution. A significant proportion of the securely provenanced material derives from funerary contexts, while sanctuary contexts appear less dominant than in central Italy. Although uneven excavation histories, publication practices, and the impact of the antiquities

market complicate contextual reconstruction, the absence in Greece of large-scale, serialised production comparable to that attested in Etruria, Latium Vetus, or Campania cannot be explained by preservation bias alone and points toward meaningful cultural differences.

Typological trends further reinforce this contrast. While the Italic evidence allows for the public visualisation of bodily nourishment and a broad range of caregiving configurations, the Greek material is characterised by more selective iconographic strategies. A particularly prominent feature of the Greek corpus is the visibility of figures associated with delegated care—such as wet nurses, nurses, pedagogues, and other caregivers—often marked by non-ideal or caricatural traits. These figures are not marginal but appear structurally central, especially in funerary contexts, where they mediate intimacy, protection, and memory. Male figures, when involved in caregiving scenes, tend to appear within delegated roles rather than as fathers, suggesting culturally specific ways of framing early childcare through service, vicarious responsibility, and household hierarchies.

The research also highlights the mobility of objects and meanings. Terracotta figurines could circulate between domestic, votive, and funerary spheres and be re-signified accordingly, generating new narratives of care, belonging, and continuity, particularly in mortuary settings. In this sense, these objects do not merely reflect social realities but actively participate in the cultural construction of care by making certain relationships visible while leaving others unrepresented.

State of the research: the Italian evidence presented here reflects established and previously published results and serves as a comparative foundation. The Greek corpus is still being expanded and systematically analysed within the ongoing project. The interpretations proposed for the Greek material should therefore be understood as provisional and intended to guide subsequent stages of research and comparative analysis.

Selected references

Albrecht, J., et al. “Religion in the Making: The Lived Ancient Religion Approach.” *Religion* 38 (2018): 1–26.

James, S. M. “Mothering: A Possible Black Feminist Link to Social Transformation?” In *Theorizing Black Feminism: The Visionary Pragmatism of Black Women*, edited by S. M. James and A. P. Busia, 44–54. New York, 1999.

McGuire, M. *Lived Religion*. Oxford, 2008.

Pedrucci, G. “Kourotrophia and ‘Mothering’ Figures: Conceiving and Raising an Infant as a Collective Process in the Greek, Etruscan, and Roman Worlds.” *Open Theology* (2020): 145–166.

Pedrucci, G. *Votive Statuettes of Adult/s and Infant/s in Ancient Italy from the End of the 7th to 3rd c. BCE: A New Reading. Ancient Latium and Etruria*. Rome: Arbor Sapientiae, 2021.

Pedrucci, G. *Votive Statuettes of Adult/s and Infant/s in Ancient Italy from the End of the 7th to 3rd c. BCE: A New Reading. Campania, Magna Graecia, and Sicily*. Rome: Arbor Sapientiae, 2022.

Image 1: Ancient Italy. Distribution of figurines by historical regions.

Image 2: Ancient Greece. Distribution of figurines by historical regions.

Image 3: Ancient Italy. Context of Figurine Findings (urban, suburban, extra-urban, funerary spaces.)¹

Image 4. Ancient Italy. Context of Figurine Findings (urban, suburban, extra-urban, funerary spaces.)

¹ The Campania graph is potentially misleading, as the vast majority of the figurines derives from Capua, a suburban context, while only a very small number of examples comes from numerous extra-urban sanctuaries. The graph is based on the number of individual sanctuaries rather than on the absolute quantity of figurines, which accounts for its potentially misleading appearance.

Image 5. Ancient Greece. Context of Figurine Findings (urban, suburban, extra-urban, funerary spaces, domestic space, workshop.)